

CREATIVE APPROACHES TO THE SOLUTION OF TASKS IN SCHOOL TEXTBOOKS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7682758>

Abstract. In this thesis, the concept of the distance between two intersecting straight lines, which is introduced as a problematic issue in general education school textbooks and has wide applications in practice, is described and the methods of finding this distance are described in detail.

Keywords: intersecting straight lines, parallel straight lines, parallel planes, distance between parallel straight lines, distance between parallel planes, volume of the pyramid.

In modern mathematics textbooks, great emphasis is placed on dividing straight lines and finding the distance between them. The reason for this can be shown by the fact that finding the distance between straight lines is widely encountered in the problems of mechanics and differential geometry and has wide applications in life.

Below are some basic definitions of bisecting straight lines and finding the distance between them, with plenty of examples. First, let's define straight lines:

Definition 1. The intersection of two straight lines that do not lie in the same plane in space are called straight lines (Fig. 1).

Figure 1

Before introducing the concept of distance between two intersecting straight lines, we define the concept of distance between two shapes.

Definition 2. For points F_1 and F_2 and arbitrary $A_1 \in F_1$, $A_2 \in F_2$ of the given forms $B_1 \in F_1$, $B_2 \in F_2$ if inequality is appropriate. Points $|A_1A_2| \leq |B_1B_2|$ are called the closest points of the given shapes. The distance between A_1 va A_2 forms means the distance between their nearest points (if it exists).

Now we present several definitions that are convenient for finding the distance between two intersecting straight lines in practice:

Definition 3. The distance between the nearest points of two intersecting straight lines is called the distance between the straight lines.

Definition 4. The distance between parallel planes where two intersecting straight lines are located is called the distance between straight lines.

Definition 5. The distance from one of the two intersecting straight lines to the parallel plane on which the second intersecting straight line lies is called the distance between these lines.

Below we show the process of solving the problem in several ways:

Problem solving. A right prism $ABCD A_1 B_1 C_1 D_1$ whose base is a square is given. If the side of the base of the prism is 4 and the height is $2\sqrt{2}$, find the distance between the diagonals DA_1 and CD_1 (Fig. 2).

Figure 2

Note: Below (ABC) - the inscription in the form ABC indicates the plane.

1-way. It is known that CD_1 lies on the diagonal $(CB_1 D_1)$. Also, from the fact that $DA_1 \parallel CB_1$ follows that the straight line $DA_1 (CB_1 D_1)$ is parallel to the plane. So, the distance between the planes DA_1 and $(CB_1 D_1)$ is equal to the distance between the diagonals DA_1 and CD_1 according to definition 5. In particular, to find this distance, it is enough to find the distance from the point A_1 of the straight line $DA_1 (CB_1 D_1)$ to the plane (Fig. 3).

Figure 3

We designate the points of intersection of the diagonals of the bases of the given right prism by O and O_1 , respectively.

It is known that the planes (ACC_1) and $(CB_1 D_1)$ intersect in the straight line $O_1 C$.

So, to find the distance from A_1 point $(CB_1 D_1)$ to the plane, it is enough to find the distance $A_1 H$ from point $O_1 C$ to the straight line $A_1 H$ (Fig. 4).

Figure 4

$BCDA_1$ – Let's look at the pyramid (Fig. 7).

Figure 7

We denote by h the height dropped from the end of this pyramid C to the base BDA_1 . The length of this height is equal to the distance between the diagonals DA_1 and CD_1 . Because this length is equal to the distance from the end C of the diagonal CD_1 to the plane BDA_1 lying on the diagonal DA_1 . We find the length of this height.

From the conditions of the problem, it can be directly found that $BD = AC = 4\sqrt{2}$, $AO = 2\sqrt{2}$. From right angle $\triangle OAA_1$ O_1 : $A_1O = CO_1 = \sqrt{AA_1^2 + AO^2} = 4$.

We find the volume of the pyramid $BCDA_1$ – through the base BDA_1 - and h - height:

$$V_{BCDA_1} = \frac{1}{3} S_{BDA_1} \cdot h = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{A_1O \cdot BD}{2} \cdot h = \frac{8\sqrt{2}}{3} \cdot h.$$

We find the volume of the pyramid $BCDA_1$ - by the base BCD – and the height AA_1 :

$$V_{BCDA_1} = \frac{1}{3} S_{BCD} \cdot AA_1 = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{BC \cdot CD}{2} \cdot AA_1 = \frac{16\sqrt{2}}{3}.$$

$$\text{So, } V_{BCDA_1} = \frac{8\sqrt{2}}{3} \cdot h = \frac{16\sqrt{2}}{3} \Rightarrow h = 2.$$

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